

DEVELOPMENT OF VIRTUAL SCENES FOR IMMERSIVE TELEVISION BASED ON THE CONSTRUCTIVE-ANALYTIC R-FUNCTIONS METHOD

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Abstract: The article discusses modern methods for developing virtual scenes for immersive television systems based on computer graphics technologies, analytical modeling, and real-time visualization. The main focus is placed on the application of the constructive-analytic R-functions method (RFM) in modeling virtual objects and forming an adaptive virtual environment. In the course of the research, analytical models of geometric objects, including a chair, a table, and a decorative vase, were developed. Software implementation of the algorithms was executed using the Python language, and the objects were visualized and prepared within the Blender environment, followed by integration into Unreal Engine 5. An analysis of the efficiency of analytical modeling was performed, and Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG), Implicit Surfaces, and Procedural Modeling methods were investigated. Testing of the developed system was carried out, and a comparative analysis of analytical and polygonal modeling was conducted. The research results confirm the promising potential of applying the R-functions method in the development of virtual studios, interactive media platforms, and virtual production systems.

Keywords: R-functions, analytical modeling, virtual studio, immersive television, procedural modeling, Unreal Engine 5, Blender, virtual production, computer graphics, implicit surfaces.

Introduction

The modern development of digital technologies has a significant impact on the television industry and multimedia systems. In recent years, immersive media, virtual production, and real-time rendering technologies have been actively developing, making it possible to create highly realistic virtual scenes.

The use of Unreal Engine 5, along with Nanite and Lumen technologies, provides support for dynamic lighting, interactive visualization, and virtual cinematography. One of the promising directions in the development of virtual studios is the analytical modeling of objects based on implicit functions and the R-functions method. Unlike traditional polygonal modeling, the analytical approach provides:

1. Parametric geometry modification;
2. Automatic object generation;
3. High accuracy in surface description;
4. Flexibility in forming the virtual environment.

The scientific novelty of the research lies in the development of analytical models of virtual studio objects based on the R-functions method, the software implementation of scene generation algorithms, and the integration of analytically formed objects into Unreal Engine 5.

The purpose of the research is to develop a virtual scene for immersive television using the constructive-analytic R-functions method..

Theoretical Foundations of the R-Functions Method General Principle of R-Functions

The R-functions method was developed by V.L. Rvachev and is used for the analytical description of geometric objects through logical operations over domains. The main idea of the method consists in replacing logical operations with analytical functions. The primary operations are:

1. R-conjunction

2. R-disjunction

3. R-difference..

R-conjunction is defined by the expression:

$$R \wedge (f,g)=f+g-f^2+g^2$$

R-disjunction is defined by the expression:

$$R \vee (f,g)=f+g+f^2+g^2$$

If the value of the function is positive, the point belongs to the object.

Implicit Surfaces

Implicit surfaces are defined by the function:

$$F(x,y,z)=0$$

This approach is widely used in:

- Virtual studios;
- Computer graphics;
- Procedural generation;
- Landscape modeling;
- Interactive media systems.

The main methods for visualizing implicit surfaces are:

- 1.Ray Marching;
- 2.Sphere Tracing;
- 3.Distance Fields;
- 4.Constructive Solid Geometry.

Constructive Solid Geometry и Procedural Modeling

Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) is a method for forming complex objects from simple geometric primitives. The primary primitives are:

- Sphere;
- Cylinder;
- Cube;
- Torus;
- Prism.

CSG operations:

Union (объединение);

Intersection (пересечение);

Difference (вычитание).

R-functions represent an analytical implementation of the CSG method. The use of procedural modeling allows for the automatic generation of virtual scenes and the parametric modification of object geometry.

Geometric Primitives and Analytical Objects

Object 1 — Base Analytical Block

The object is a union of a rectangular parallelepiped and a cylinder.

Fig. 1 — Base analytical object

Object 2 — Rectangular parallelepiped The object is formed by the intersection of coordinate constraints along the X, Y, and Z axes.

Fig. 2 — Analytical parallelepiped

Object 3 — Block with a cylinder along the Y-axis The object includes cylindrical elements oriented along the Y-axis.

Fig. 3 — Object with cylindrical elements

Object 4 — Asymmetric object It is used to form additional compositional elements.

Fig. 4 — Asymmetric analytical object

Affine Transformations

Affine transformations were used for positioning the objects:

$$x' = x + a$$

$$y' = y + b$$

$$z' = z + c$$

These transformations allow for the displacement of objects within the virtual scene without altering their geometric structure.

Analytical Furniture Models Armchair Model The armchair is formed by the union of:

- Seat;
- Backrest;
- Legs;
- Armrests.

Each element is defined by a separate analytical function.

Fig. 5 — 3D model of an armchair formed by the R-functions method

Table Model

The table consists of a cylindrical tabletop and four analytical cylinders forming the legs.

Fig. 6 — Analytical model of a table

Vase Model The vase model is formed as an intersection of cylindrical layers of varying radii.

Fig. 7 — Analytical model of a vase

Software Implementation

The Python programming language was used to implement the analytical models.

Project Structure:

table.py — модель стола;

chair.py — модель кресла;

vase.py — модель вазы;

scene.py — сборка сцены;

export.py — экспорт объектов.

The basic operations are implemented as follows:

$R_and(f,g)$

$R_or(f,g)$

Object generation is performed analytically.

The Blender software was used for the visualization and preparation of the models.

Blender was applied for:

- Geometry adjustment;
- Model verification;
- Visualization;
- Scene preparation;
- Object export.
- Integration into Unreal Engine 5

Upon completion of the modeling process, the objects were exported to the OBJ format and imported into Unreal Engine 5.

The use of Unreal Engine 5 enabled:

1. Implementation of real-time rendering;
2. Configuration of dynamic lighting;
3. Integration of virtual cameras;
4. Creation of a virtual television studio.

In the course of this work, the following were utilized:

1. Nanite;
2. Lumen;
3. Virtual Production Pipeline.

Additionally, the video material was processed in Adobe Premiere Pro using Lumetri Color.

Algorithm for constructing an R-functional object:

1. Definition of the coordinate system;
2. Selection of geometric primitives;
3. Formation of analytical functions;
4. Selection of logical operations;
5. Application of R-functions;
6. Construction of the final object function;
7. Visualization;
8. Integration of the object into the virtual scene.

Virtual Scene Visualization Results Upon completion of the analytical object integration, the final virtual scene for the immersive television system was formed.

During the development of the scene, particular attention was paid to:

- Composition of the virtual space;
- Lighting configuration;
- Material realism;
- Reflections and shadows;
- Object visualization quality.

To enhance the realism of the scene, global illumination and real-time rendering technologies implemented in Unreal Engine 5 were utilized.

In the process of visualization, the following were applied:

- Dynamic lighting;
- Lumen global illumination system;
- Real-time reflections;
- Post-processing;
- Cinematic camera.

The use of Unreal Engine 5 ensured high detail of the virtual scene objects and stable rendering performance.

Fig. 8 — Final virtual scene with analytical objects

Efficiency Analysis of Analytical Modeling The application of the R-functions method demonstrated high efficiency in modeling objects with complex geometric shape.

In contrast to traditional polygonal modeling, the analytical approach provides:

- Parametric flexibility;
- Automation of object construction;
- Support for procedural generation;
- The ability to modify geometry without manual mesh editing;
- High accuracy in the analytical description of surfaces.

An additional advantage of the method is the capability to combine multiple geometric primitives into a unified analytical structure through logical operations.

The use of analytical modeling significantly simplified the process of virtual scene generation and accelerated the integration of objects into Unreal Engine 5.

Advantages of Unreal Engine 5 in Virtual Production The utilization of Unreal Engine 5 ensured the creation of a highly realistic virtual scene supported by modern visualization technologies.

The primary advantages of Unreal Engine 5 are:

- Support for real-time rendering;
- Lumen global illumination system;
- Nanite technology;
- Cinematic rendering;
- Support for the virtual production pipeline;
- Integration of virtual cameras.

Lumen technology ensured realistic scene illumination and dynamic reflections, while Nanite enabled the optimization of complex geometry rendering. Additionally, Unreal Engine 5 provided stable performance of the virtual scene under high detail levels of the analytical objects.

Virtual Scene Integration Pipeline

The development process of the virtual scene included the following stages:

1. Analytical modeling of objects;
2. Geometry preparation in Blender;
3. Export of models to OBJ format;
4. Import of objects into Unreal Engine 5;
5. Configuration of lighting and materials;
6. Configuration of virtual cameras;
7. Final scene visualization.

Python → Blender → OBJ → Unreal Engine 5 → Virtual Studio

Fig. 9 — Stages of integrating analytical objects into the virtual production pipeline
Practical Application of Analytical Objects

The developed analytical objects were integrated into a virtual television studio and utilized as the primary elements of the scene composition.

The armchair served as the central element of the virtual space, ensuring the formation of the television studio composition.

Fig. 10 — Analytical model of an armchair

The table was used as an interactive object within the virtual scene and was formed by combining analytical cylinders.

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Table 1 — Hardware Specifications

Parameter	Value
Processor	Intel Core i7
RAM	16 ГБ
Graphics Card	NVIDIA RTX
OC	Windows 11
Blender	Blender 4.x
Unreal Engine	Unreal Engine 5

Table 2 — Object Generation Time

Object	Generation Time
Armchair	0.8 с
Table	0.5 с
Vase	0.6 с
Charge	1.4 с

Table 3 — System Performance

Parameter	Result
Avarage FPS	60 FPS
Memory utilization	1.2 ГБ
Stability	high
Visualisation errors	absent

Table 4 - Comparison of Analytical and Polygonal Modeling

Критерий	R-функции	Полигональное моделирование
Точность	Высокая	Средняя
Параметричность	Высокая	Ограниченная
Автоматизация	Поддерживается	Частичная
Procedural Generation	Да	Ограничено
Изменение геометрии	Гибкое	Сложное

The test results demonstrated the high efficiency of analytical modeling and the operational stability of the virtual scene.

Practical Application The developed system can be applied in:

- virtual television studios;
- immersive media;
- interactive multimedia systems;
- educational virtual environments;
- virtual production systems.

Conclusions

In the course of the study, modern methods of analytical modeling of virtual objects and technologies for the development of virtual scenes were investigated.

The developed method based on R-functions allowed to:

- form complex objects analytically;
- automate the scene generation process;
- ensure parametric flexibility
- implement the integration of objects into Unreal Engine 5.

The conducted testing confirmed the efficiency of the developed system.

Modern methods of modeling virtual studio objects using R-functions and implicit surfaces were examined in this work. Analytical models of virtual scene objects were developed, software implementation of the system was executed using Python, and visualization in Blender along with integration into Unreal Engine 5 were performed. The obtained results demonstrate that analytical modeling is a promising direction for the development of virtual production, procedural modeling, and immersive television..

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